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**PERCEIVED AWARENESS AND INVOLVEMENT IN PLAGIARISM
AND USE OF TURNITIN IN RESEARCH PRACTICE AMONG POST-GRADUATE
STUDENTS IN CROSS RIVER: IMPLICATIONS FOR ASSESSMENT**

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Abstract

This study examined the perceived awareness and involvement in plagiarism and use of Turnitin in research practice among postgraduate students in universities in Cross River State. The survey research design was adopted for the study. Four research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The population comprised all the Ph.D, Masters, and Post-graduate Diploma students during the 2014 – 2017 sessions in the two public universities and numbered 4,441. A sample of 444 was drawn through stratified and purposive sampling techniques and made up of students who were involved in post graduate defense at three major levels- proposal, post field and final. The instrument designed by the researchers titled "Awareness/Involvement in Plagiarism – Turnitin Practice Questionnaire" was duly validated and used for the data collection. Cronbach reliability coefficient alpha of this instrument which was 0.76 for section C was considered high enough to elicit the desired response. Statistical tools employed include descriptive statistics, inferential statistics and thematic analysis. Results were presented from the analysis and conclusion on the findings included that students are aware of plagiarism and the perceived usefulness of turnitin was ascertained as a tool that can enhance quality writing among others. Part of the conclusion was that there exists evidence of some level of involvement as indicated in some of the responses of the students which calls for the implementation of the recommendations made in this study. The study findings had implication for assessment. One of such implications is that students should be given more tasks on writing of term papers hence, assessment should target research skills such as information gathering, paraphrasing, summarizing, referencing within text and quotation among others.

Keywords: Awareness, Involvement level, Plagiarism, Usefulness, Turnitin, Post- graduate Students, Assessment.

Introduction

Functional education will continue to be the bane for development in science and technology in our nation. Hence, research product is to be continually relied upon for growth and development of the economy. To achieve this, there is need for improved graduate research practices in public universities in Nigeria and in Cross River State in particular. More so, due to the global quest for intellectuals who can actually solve society's problems, it behooves on university education to train graduates who can think divergently and creatively. Therefore, if students are helped to develop these divergent thinking and creative skills, they would be more likely to be independent and less involved in dishonest practices such as plagiarism.

Plagiarism is taking the words, ideas and labour of other people and giving the impression and or pretending that they are your own, thereby crediting the idea, opinion, and thought to oneself (Pyer, 2000). It is the "wrongful appropriation" and stealing and publication of another author's language, thoughts, ideas or expressions and the representation of them as one's own original work (Wikipedia). This act is morally wrong and synonymous to robbery. The consequences of plagiarism are far reaching. It negates the main objective of research; it truncates the process of generating new facts that can contribute to existing literature about a phenomenon, and reveals the lapses in training in university education. The art of plagiarism contributes to fallen standard of education. Creativity and good research practice is relegated to the back while plagiarism thrives to destroy university education.

Academicians or lecturers and students have been found to engage in one form of academic dishonest or the other including plagiarism. The involvement in this dishonest behavior has been attributed to both personal and contextual factors including inadequate training, lack of self-control, financial constraint to conduct genuine and fresh research, peer cheating behavior and perceived severity of punishment. (McCabe, Trama & Butterfield, 2002).

Idika (2016) noted a lot more of the negative academic research behavior including some fraudulent practices as submitting plagiarized or copied assignments and term papers, presenting already presented research proposal as if it is their own effort, contracting paper writing, among others. Building on this background, students plagiarize for several reasons. According to Gullifer and Tyson (2010) and Walker (2009), students are motivated to plagiarize because: inadequate time to study; fear of failure perceived between actual grade and student's personal effort; student studying so many courses that results to a lot of work per semester; a believe that student will not be caught because lecturers do not have time to read extensively the assignments because of work pressure; motivation of doing well of getting good grade; student feeling of alienation by colleagues; and student individual factors such as age, grade average point, gender and others (Gullifer & Tyson, 2010, p. 465).

Betts, Bostock, Elder and Trueman (2012) reported similar factors for academic dishonest among university students but added a number of others which include lack of proper orientation or integration of students in the culture of academic community, part-time employment which affects student study time, parental pressure that demands students to

perform well, lack of study skills and student-lecturer rapport which prevents lecturers from punishing students for plagiarizing and mass copying among themselves. Unfortunately too, it was observed by Asim, Kalu and Ekwueme (2007) that a careful search into many postgraduate research works indicates an increasing breach of such traditions as clear statement of problems, adequate review of literature, proper documentation, appropriate research methodology that should give rise to valid and reliable data analytic techniques and adequate interpretation of research results, all because most students have become familiar with dishonest research writing.

Several strategies and methods have been and are being utilized by institutions to curb plagiarism among academics both students and lecturers. These strategies include plagiarism policies, examination malpractice ban, quality assurance/control and stringent scrutiny and assessment of students' submissions by supervisors and course lecturers. Despite all these control measures, plagiarism still persists in universities in the study area.

To check plagiarism behavior, Turnitin should become a part of an individual's research tool for self-evaluation and improvement. As a result, graduate students would have a rethink on the erroneous new idea about Turnitin as a witch hunting criteria for submission of theses and dissertations. Let's recall that the Turnitin system was introduced into the university system in Nigeria as a tool to address the issue of academic integrity or dishonesty and perhaps to salvage the image of the system as falling in comparison with other developing countries, whose products have been rated higher. The main use of Turnitin is to check for similarity and potential instance of plagiarism in students' papers, theses and dissertations. This study is hinged on the control theory of crime and delinquency by Hirschi (1969) and social learning theory by Albert Bandura (1977) that will be discussed at the later of this introduction.

The present study is predicated on the outcome of reflections on the theme of the conference, and also on the education policy statement "that a greater proportion of expenditure on university education shall be devoted to science and technology". It would not be inappropriate if one interprets it to be that public universities in Nigeria and the ones in Cross River State have been equipped to develop students with scientific and technological skills for the nation's economic development. This study presumes that one of the ways to achieve this developmental goal is to encourage creativity, problem solving skills and the scientific attitudes, which are attitudes that increase academic writing skills, encourage originality in research writing while discouraging copying of any kind without referencing the source, and at same time create awareness about the negative consequences of plagiarism and reduce its involvement among graduate students. As at now, Turnitin has come to stay as a study regulation for Research Degree Programmes in some universities. However, what looked like Turnitin has been the traditional checks and scoring of students' work by lecturers according to the peculiar marking rubrics which observably have not been effective in checking plagiarism. Hence, students have been assessed on plagiarized work and certificated without even acquiring the expected skills only to be pushed into the world of work to increase the unemployability condition in the labour market.

Therefore, the study assessed the perceived awareness and involvement in plagiarism and usefulness of Turnitin among graduate students, with the view to advising university educators on the way forward towards improved quality in assessment for functional education.

Awareness refers to the knowledge about an object or event, the competence or skills as well as the methods of operation. It has to do with background knowledge about the object, event or any other phenomenon (Reinhardt, Mlelko, Sloep and Drachslor, 2015). Through awareness of something, one is able to discriminate between the right or the wrong thing to do, that is, whether to plagiarize or not. However, studies show that some plagiarisms are unintentional, hence, can be regarded as poor practice in research. In that case, what would a researcher or a graduate student be thinking when he or she submits works done with materials without clearly indicating by referencing that the material copied or paraphrased came from some other sources?

Orim, Borg and Awala – Ale (2013) stressed that most plagiarism cases occurred as a result of lack of awareness and proper skills. These authors conducted a study on Nigerian students on post graduate programme in United Kingdom (UK) and found that most of the post-graduate students are not aware of what actually constitutes plagiarism before coming to UK universities.

Ryan, Bonanno, Krass, Scouller and Smith (2009) in a study on undergraduate and postgraduate pharmacy students' perceptions of plagiarism and academic honesty discovered that there is widespread deficiency in students' understanding of plagiarism across all years of undergraduate and post graduate pharmacy students in university of Sydney, Australia. This finding would imply that the students under survey at the time are unaware of plagiarism hence, are involved in it unknowingly.

Involvement refers to taking part in the behavior associated with plagiarism. Lecturers, for example detect plagiarism during marking and assessment of students' submissions (term papers, assignments, examination scripts). Similarity of copied works among students can be said to be an act of involvement in plagiarism, showing that the source of the work is somewhere. However, some authors maintain that involvement in plagiarism may be intentional which is sometimes or unknowingly because they are unclear of what constitutes proper way to take note, paraphrase or make quotation due to poor skills in academic writing (Onuoha & Ikonne, 2013).

Chukwuemeka, Gbenga, Sunday and Ndidiamaka (2013) studied academic dishonesty among Nigerian pharmacy students in comparison to their United Kingdom counterparts and found that the perception of Nigerian students as regards academic dishonesty in the universities investigated was poor, and the students' involvement in cheating was much higher than what was reported in US and UK schools. Maina, Maina and Jaaros' (2014) report of a research that was conducted in University of Florida as far back as 1987 showed 68.1 percent of the students involved in plagiarism and other forms of academic misconducts.

Usefulness refers to importance attached to the use of Turnitin software in the university. Studies show that Turnitin is very useful for checking plagiarism in students' submissions (assignments, theses, dissertations etc). According to the Queen's University Belfast, if Turnitin is used at an early stage in students' theses for example, it can help prevent issues at a more critical stage of the development of the theses.

The use of Turnitin is however, limited because it does not address subject areas that are more practice-based outcomes like music. Also, guidelines for the use of Turnitin software from the Centre of Educational Development (<http://www.qub.ac.uk/cite2write>) warns that the software does not make a judgment on whether a student has plagiarized in his or her thesis, hence, this aspect should be determined at the discretion of the supervisor's academic judgment. To note here is, supervisor of students' work have to be trained regarding how to similarly report, as there are no defined percentage of matching text which determines extent of plagiarism in a submitted work. This matter has been tackled by the University of Calabar. Who puts the percentage similarity index at below 10 percent.

The much gathered from literature on usefulness of plagiarism reveals that basically it is used for checking of similarity index and that it is a good practice. University of Calabar, Cross River State subscribed to the Turnitin software as a means to help improve quality of writing among students. It is against this background that this study sought to assess awareness/involvement and Turnitin practice among graduate students of public universities in Cross River State.

This study finds support in the control theory of crime and delinquency by Hirshi (1969) and social learning theory by Albert Bandura (1997). The control theory posits that man has a natural tendency to deviate hence, a control must be in place to check this deviation in behavior. The relevance of this theory to this work dwells on the fact that plagiarism is a behavior that has been considered synonymous to stealing of another person's copyright because, the person involved has copied a part of somebody else's work without appropriate acknowledgement. Before now, checks for plagiarism in students work was largely by manual through careful scrutiny of students submissions by their lecturers and supervisors, but now, a software package called Turnitin is currently used by universities who have subscribed to it to check for similarity index in order to detect plagiarism in students' works. This Turnitin serves as a control to prevent involvement in plagiarism.

The social learning theory by Albert Bandura (1977) posits that behavior is largely acquired through imitation and observational learning. By observing this a person conceptualizes how new behaviors are performed and on later occasions, this coded information serves as a guide for reproduction by modeling. The relevance of this theory to this study is that plagiarism which is a behavior (dishonest behavior) can be learned through modeling. Students copy one another and submit for grading. Another student observing that the behavior is rewarding also involves in the act and gets away with it as well. This theory takes care of students' awareness of the act of plagiarism and involvement in it. Based on the foregoing, the study assumes that the respondents may not be honest in their responses to the items in the study.

To aid the study four research questions were posed

1. Are graduate students of the two universities aware of plagiarism?
2. What is the perceived level of involvement in plagiarism among graduate students of the two universities?
3. How useful is Turnitin in reducing plagiarism among graduate students of the two universities?
4. What are the major themes in the graduate students' responses on the usefulness of Turnitin?

Further more two hypotheses were formulated

1. There is no significant influence of respondents' institutions(graduate students of UNICAL and CRUTECH) on their awareness of plagiarism.
2. There is no significant difference in the perceived level of involvement in plagiarism between graduate students of UNICAL and CRUTECH.

Method

The research design adopted by this study was the descriptive survey design. The study examined the perceived awareness and involvement in plagiarism and the use of turnitin in research practice among post-graduate students in Cross River State. It also examined the implication for assessment. The stratified random sampling and purposive sampling techniques were used to select a sample of four hundred and forty-four (444) post-graduate research students from the total of 4,441 number of post graduate students in the two public universities in Cross River State. This population comprised all the Ph.D, Masters and Post-graduate Diploma students admitted between 2014 and 2017 academic sessions and who are currently embarking on research at those three levels of programme. The sample of the postgraduate students who were involved in postgraduate defense at the three major levels- proposal, post field and final defense were purposefully picked because they were students who had reached project stage to be able to handle issues of plagiarism. The instrument used for data collection was a researcher constructed questionnaire titled "Awareness/Involvement in Plagiarism and Turnitin Practice Questionnaire". This was validated by three experts, two from Measurement and Evaluation and one from Psychology. The instrument had four sections: Section A gathered information on demographic data (sex, name of institution, class of graduate student, and level of thesis). Section B elicited information on perceived awareness of plagiarism, measured as "Aware" and "Not aware", Section C elicited information on perceived level of involvement in plagiarism and responses were based on a four point scale of strongly agree (for very highly involved), agree (highly involved), disagree (low involvement) and strongly disagree (Not involved); and Section D, which had one question that elicited information on their perception of the usefulness of Turnitin practice and their reasons for the expressed views. The reasons yielded from the students' three response patterns (very useful, fairly useful and not useful) in this part of the instrument were summarized under ten most popular themes. Cronbach reliability coefficient alpha of the

instrument which is 0.76 for section C was considered high enough to elicit the desired response. Statistical tools employed for analysis included frequency, percentage, chi-square, independent t-test and thematic analysis.

Results

1. Are graduate students of the two universities aware of plagiarism?

Table 1: Perceived awareness of plagiarism among graduate students of the two universities

	FREQUENCY	%
AWARE	398	89.6
NOT AWRE	46	10.4
Total	444	100

Out of the 444 respondents sampled, 398 are aware of plagiarism representing 89.6% of the respondents while 46 of the respondents were unaware representing 10.4% of the respondent.

2. What is the perceived level of involvement in plagiarism among graduate students of the two universities?

Table 2: Perceived level of involvement in plagiarism among graduate students of the two universities

LEVEL OF INVOLVEMENT	FREQUENCY	%
LOW	222	50.0
MODERATE	168	37.8
HIGH	54	12.2
TOTAL	444	100.0

Out of the 444 respondents sampled, 222 have a perceived low level of involvement in plagiarism representing 50% of the respondents, 168(37.8%) have a perceived moderate level of involvement in plagiarism while 54(12.2%) of the respondents have a perceived high level of involvement in plagiarism.

3. How useful is turnitin in reducing plagiarism among graduate students of the two universities?

This was answered based on the three response patterns used to elicit the information. The results of students' responses spread across the three response patterns are as follows:

- Very useful (234 representing 52.70% of the responses)
- Fairly useful (120 representing 27.03% of the responses)
- Not useful (90 representing 20.27% of the responses)

4. What are the major themes in the graduate students' responses on the usefulness of Turnitin? This was an open-ended question which asked respondents to give reasons for their choice about their view of Turnitin practice in relation to plagiarism. The several opinions given were summarized under ten (10) themes as follows:
1. Ensures originality
 2. Gives a writer confidence
 3. Increases academic writing skills
 4. Checks plagiarism
 5. Encourages divergent thinking for novel research
 6. Makes one more knowledgeable about research writing report
 7. Encourages hard work
 8. Provides validity for ones work
 9. Increases the value of copyright
 10. For authenticity

Table 3: Simple percentage analysis of the responses of respondents to perceived level of involvement in plagiarism

S/N	STATEMENT	SA	%	A	%	D	%	SD	%
1	Using a student's research proposal to reshape another shouldn't mean anything to anybody	60	13.5	90	20.3	216	48.6	78	17.6
2	Adjusting the topic but leave contents the same is not totally bad	108	24.3	162	36.5	120	27.0	54	12.2
3	Using an author's words but cites another in place should be part of the norm	84	18.9	126	28.4	180	40.5	54	12.2
4	Duplicating part of someone's work and submit as my own effort is no big deal	42	9.5	96	21.6	120	27.0	186	41.9
5	Copying verbatim from a work may never be discovered	54	12.2	144	32.4	204	45.9	54	12.2
6	Generating data to suit a research purpose	60	13.5	138	31.1	144	32.4	102	23.0
7	Adopting somebody's research instrument as part of my effort is part of sharing in research	114	25.7	198	44.6	72	16.2	60	13.5
8	Adapting an instrument without referencing the source may be a mistake that is pardonable	180	40.5	126	28.4	84	18.9	54	12.2
9	Adapting someone's data analysis result in my work to save time is part of collaborating in research.	246	55.4	96	21.6	60	13.5	42	9.5
10	Carrying out proper trial test on my research instrument may not be necessary for my pre-field.	102	23.0	72	16.2	120	27.0	150	33.8
11	Extrapolating data to make up the sample size needed for my work is a good research practice.	42	9.5	168	37.8	180	40.5	54	12.2
12	Referencing all works used in my thesis or dissertation can be possible	90	20.3	84	18.9	84	18.9	186	41.9

Table 3 shows the simple percentage analysis of the responses of post graduate students to the perceived level of involvement in plagiarism in universities in Cross River State. The table indicated that out of the 12 items in the table, 7 items (1,3,4,5,6,10,11) showed greater percentage of students' responses to perception of low involvement in plagiarism than items 2,7,8,9 and 12 which showed perception of higher involvement.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant influence of respondents' institution (graduate students of UNICAL and CRUTECH) on their awareness of plagiarism.

Table 4: Chi-Square showing influence of respondents' institution (graduate students of UNICAL and CRUTECH) on their awareness of plagiarism

	Awareness		df	χ^2	p-value
	Aware	Not Aware			
Unical	243 (54.7%)	40 (9%)	1	11.969	0.001*
Crutech	155 (34.9%)	6 (1.4%)			

*P-value < 0.05

Given that chi-square value of 11.969 and p-value of 0.001 < 0.05, the results showed that the respondents' institutions (graduate students of UNICAL and CRUTECH) have a significant influence on their awareness of plagiarism.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the perceived level of involvement in plagiarism between graduate students of UNICAL and CRUTECH.

Table 5: Independent t-test showing difference in the perceived level of involvement in plagiarism between graduate students of UNICAL and CRUTECH

Institution	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	t	p-value	
Plagiarism	Unical	283	26.6714	7.34471	442	-1.118	0.214
	Crutech	161	27.4658	6.93004			

P > .05

In the Table 5, given the t-value of -1.118, df = 442 and p-value = 0.214 > 0.05, the results indicated that there is no significant difference in the perceived level of involvement in plagiarism between graduate students of UNICAL and CRUTECH.

Discussion

From the results of the study, it was found that graduate students of the two universities sampled are aware of plagiarism. These findings contradict the study of Ryan, Bonanno,

Krass, Scouller and Smith (2009) in a study on undergraduate and postgraduate pharmacy students' perceptions of plagiarism and academic honesty which found a widespread deficiency in students' understanding of plagiarism across all years of undergraduate and post graduate pharmacy students in university of Sydney, Australia. This finding of Ryan et al (2009) would imply that the students under survey at the time were unaware of plagiarism hence, were involved in it unknowingly. The reason for the present findings could be that the introduction of Turnitin in the university has enlightened many students on the evil of plagiarism practice which has long term consequences such as twisting policy evidence and taking decision on false information. The high level of awareness has shown that the result can be explained on the fact that graduate students are now required more than ever before to submit their thesis proposals and final theses for anti -plagiarism (Turnitin) check. This is especially a requirement that cuts across higher institutions of learning. However, between the two Universities, it is the University of Calabar that has installed the anti-plagiarism software. This is indicated by the higher awareness of graduate students in the University of Calabar as shown in the result.

The result of hypothesis two shows the level of involvement in plagiarism to be statistically not different across the institutions. This implies that the level of involvement in plagiarism between the graduate students of the two institutions under study is not significant. This sprung up a surprise. The surprise is on the differences on level of involvement expected of graduate students of UNICAL who the result of the study has shown to be more enlightened because of TURNITIN anti-plagiarism device emphasized in their institution. Ordinarily, the application of anti-plagiarism device in student research practice should command some level of influence on their behaviour in research conduct.

Unfortunately, the result showed otherwise. The researchers perceive that this may be attributed to their earlier assumption that respondents may not be honest in their responses due to the nature of the items which probe ones morality. However, this result aligns with the finding of Onuoha and Ikonne (2013) that involvement in plagiarism may be intentional. The authors also added that sometimes involvement may be unknowingly because they are unclear of what constitutes proper way to take note, paraphrase or make quotation due to poor skills in academic writing. In order to further explain the play out of our assumption in this study that respondents may not be honest in their responses, item numbers 2, 7, 8, 9 and 12 on table 3 revealed level of intentional involvement. This calls for lecturers' responsiveness in devising innovative ways of detecting plagiarism in their supervision of students' work in order to guide them ethically.

On usefulness, more than average number of the respondents sampled opined that turnitin was useful. This is supported by University of Calabar that their reason for subscribing to turnitin software device was to help improve quality of writing among students. Thematic analysis of students' responses sampled from the two universities under study reviewed so many usefulness of turnitin. These were captured under ten themes as presented in the result section of this report.

Conclusion

From the findings, it can be concluded that graduate students of the two universities have a significant level of awareness of plagiarism, and the perceived usefulness of turnitin was ascertained as a tool that can enhance quality writing among others. However, there exists evidence of some level of involvement as indicated in some of the responses of the students which calls for the implementation of the recommendations made in this study.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Orientate graduate students more on plagiarism and need for originality in their work. Greater commitment of lecturers/ supervisors of researches to ethically guide students through adequate mentorship, workshop and seminars will help to achieve the above and sustain integrity in research.
2. Through induction programme, graduate students should be made fully aware of the use and general function of Turnitin. For example, this will desensitize the erroneous belief by some that it is a witch-hunting exercise to delay their graduation.

Implication for assessment

1. More of term paper writing tasks should be given to graduate students to inculcate relevant skills in research practice.
2. Grading the students' work by lecturers and supervisors should target key areas of research skills such as problem articulation, literature search, reporting, referencing, paraphrasing, summarizing among others.

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